

MEDICAL SCIENCES

LEUKOCYTE PROFILING IN MALIGNANT PLEURAL EFFUSIONS: A CYTOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE ON DIAGNOSTIC ADVANCES

**Aleksiev V.,
Yavorov B.,**

*Department of Cardiovascular Surgery, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, BGR
Thoracic Surgery Clinic, UMHAT Kaspela, Plovdiv, BGR*

Markov D.,

*Department of General and Clinical Pathology, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, BGR
Department of Clinical Pathology, UMHAT Pulmed, Plovdiv, BGR*

Karlyukov M.,

Thoracic Surgery Clinic, UMHAT Kaspela, Plovdiv, BGR

Shterev F.,

Kartev S.,

*Section Pneumology and Physiatics, Department of Internal Diseases, Medical University of Plovdiv,
Plovdiv, BGR*

Thoracic Surgery Clinic, UMHAT Kaspela, Plovdiv, BGR

Bechev K.

*Department of General and Clinical Pathology, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, BGR
Department of Neurosurgery, UMHAT Pulmed, Plovdiv, BGR*

Abstract

Malignant pleural effusions (MPEs) are a severe clinical complication affecting approximately one million individuals annually. Characterized by fluid accumulation in the pleural cavity, MPEs significantly impair quality of life and are associated with a poor prognosis. This study explores the cytological profiles of pleural fluid in patients with MPEs and benign pleural diseases. Using a case-control approach involving 151 Bulgarian patients, we analyzed leukocyte populations in several pleural fluid samples. The Mann-Whitney U test identified significant differences in total leukocyte counts (TLC) and monocyte counts between groups, while Spearman's analysis highlighted correlations between hematological and biochemical parameters. Findings underscore the diagnostic utility of leukocyte subpopulation profiling. These markers offer promise in improving diagnostic accuracy and tailoring patient management strategies in MPEs.

Keywords: malignant pleura effusion, leukocyte profiling, eosinophilia, diagnostic differentiation, pleural lymphocytosis.

Introduction

Malignant pleural effusions (MPE) represent a significant clinical challenge with profound medical and socioeconomic implications. Affecting nearly one million people annually, MPEs are a major cause of severe breathlessness and diminished quality of life [1]. As a common complication in cancer patients, approximately 20% of individuals with malignancies develop pleural effusions during the course of their illness [2]. The prognosis for MPE is often poor, with median survival rates ranging from 4 to 9 months, contingent on cancer type and stage [3]. These figures emphasize the urgency of early detection and the establishment of effective diagnostic and therapeutic strategies to alleviate the burden on both patients and healthcare systems.

Understanding the mechanisms behind pleural effusion formation is crucial for managing its symptoms and causes. Normal pleural fluid is a clear, straw-colored liquid maintained by a delicate balance between production and clearance. Disruptions to this equilibrium—whether due to increased hydrostatic pressure, reduced oncotic pressure, or impaired lymphatic drainage—can lead to fluid accumulation in the pleural cavity.

From a diagnostic perspective, cytological analysis of pleural fluid offers valuable insights. Normal

pleural fluid predominantly comprises cells of the monocyte-macrophage lineage, with lymphocytes and mesothelial cells accounting for smaller proportions [4]. Inflammatory effusions show elevated white blood cell counts, while malignant effusions often present with tumor cells, confirmed through cytopathological evaluation [5]. Pleural lymphocytosis commonly indicates tuberculosis or chronic conditions like rheumatoid arthritis and lymphoma, while eosinophilia may arise in malignant, idiopathic, or parapneumonic effusions [6].

In the differential cytological analysis of normal pleural fluid, the highest proportion of observed cells belongs to the white blood cell lineage, amounting to 1.716×10^3 cells/mL. Of these, cells from the monocyte-macrophage system comprise approximately 70–75%. Lymphocytes account for about 23%, while mesothelial cells are marginally represented, at only 1–2%. The differential count also highlights populations of polymorphonuclear leukocytes (neutrophils), eosinophils, and undifferentiated cells [50].

Various pathologies of the pleural space result in diverse changes in the composition and proportions of these cells. Inflammatory diseases associated with pleural effusions, for instance, lead to an increased number of white blood cells, with bacterial infections

further stimulating the expression of polymorphonuclear leukocytes. Certain malignant diseases, such as lymphomas and leukemias associated with pleural infiltration, are characterized by an increased percentage of the affected cell lineage in pleural punctates [7].

Pleural lymphocytosis is highly suggestive of a tuberculous pleural effusion (TPE), although chronic pleural effusions also exhibit high lymphocyte differentiation, often exceeding 50%. The most common causes of pleural lymphocytosis include tuberculosis, pleural carcinomatosis, chronic congestive heart failure, lymphoma, liver failure, rheumatoid arthritis, and recent coronary intervention [8].

An increased percentage of eosinophils is described in malignant diseases affecting the pleura, parapneumonic pleural effusions, and in 25% of cases, the etiology remains idiopathic [9].

Materials and methods

To meet the study's objectives, a cross-sectional observational case-control investigation was carried out involving Bulgarian patients diagnosed with pleural effusions. The study included 151 participants. The control group comprised 72 individuals with confirmed benign conditions through follow-up biopsy. Among these, 38 cases were inflammatory in nature, while the remaining 34 were non-inflammatory pleural effusions. Malignant pleural involvement was identified in 79 patients, representing the primary types of pleural pathology in this cohort.

Pleural fluid samples were collected using sealed biological material containers during thoracentesis or intraoperative procedures such as VATS. Part of each sample was allocated for biochemical analysis, while

the remainder was designated for tumor marker evaluation and cytological testing.

Statistical methods were selected based on the study's aims, variable types, and established practices in thoracic surgery research. Data organization, processing, and analysis were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics software package, focusing on quantitative and qualitative variables. Empirical findings were summarized in tables and illustrated with relevant graphs created in MS Office 365.

To validate the analysis results, the following statistical approaches were applied:

- **Mann-Whitney U Test:** A non-parametric method for comparing two independent groups to assess differences in parameter distributions.

- **Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test:** A non-parametric test examining whether a dataset conforms to a theoretical distribution.

- **Independent Samples t-test:** A parametric test comparing the mean values of two independent groups.

- **Levene's Test for Equality of Variances:** A method for evaluating variance consistency across groups.

Results

The normality of the variables was assessed using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. All variables, including Total Leukocyte Count (TLC), Segment Neutrophils (SEG), Monocytes (MON), and Lymphocytes (LYMPH), showed significant deviations from a normal distribution ($p < 0.001$). These results indicate that the data is non-normally distributed as shown on Table 1.

Table 1

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test conducted for all parameters

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	N	Normal Parameters		Most Extreme Differences			Test Statistic	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Absolute	Positive	Negative		
TLC	151	119.77	175.413	.264	.264	-.253	.264	<.001
SEG	151	15.88	17.672	.238	.238	-.203	.238	<.001
MON	151	5.91	3.001	.137	.137	-.073	.137	<.001
LYMPH	151	78.12	19.168	.214	.162	-.214	.214	<.001

The Independent Samples t-test, accompanied by Levene's test for equality of variances, revealed no significant differences between groups for any of the studied variables. Levene's test confirmed the assumption

of equal variances for all variables ($p > 0.05$). Additionally, the t-test results for TLC ($p = 0.296$), SEG ($p = 0.794$), MON ($p = 0.079$), and LYMPH ($p = 0.563$) suggest that the means of these variables were not significantly different across groups.

Table 2

The Independent Samples Test carried out for our variables

		Independent Samples Test									
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper	
TLC	Equal variances assumed	.874	.351	-1.050	149	.296	-29.993	28.57	-86.449	26.464	
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.071	133.3	.286	-29.993	28.01	-85.385	25.399	
SEG	Equal variances assumed	.549	.460	-.261	149	.794	-.754	2.888	-6.462	4.953	
	Equal variances not assumed			-.259	140.5	.796	-.754	2.909	-6.506	4.997	
MON	Equal variances assumed	.338	.562	-1.768	149	.079	-.858	.486	-1.817	.101	
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.757	141.9	.081	-.858	.488	-1.824	.108	
LYMPH	Equal variances assumed	.867	.353	.580	149	.563	1.816	3.130	-4.369	8.001	
	Equal variances not assumed			.575	138.2	.566	1.816	3.157	-4.427	8.060	

The Mann-Whitney U test, a non-parametric alternative, highlighted significant group differences for TLC (p = 0.048) and MON (p = 0.017). However, no significant differences were observed for SEG (p =

0.321) or LYMPH (p = 0.075). These findings suggest that TLC and MON values vary significantly between groups, while SEG and LYMPH do not.

Table 3

The Mann-Whitney U Test done using our chosen parameters

Mann-Whitney U Test

	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
TLC	2313.000	4941.000	-1.979	.048
SEG	2578.500	5206.500	-.993	.321
MON	2207.500	4835.500	-2.387	.017
LYMPH	2366.000	5526.000	-1.783	.075

Spearman's correlation analysis identified several significant associations between the studied variables. TLC exhibited a positive correlation with MON (r = 0.435, p < 0.001) and a negative correlation with

LYMPH (r = -0.488, p < 0.001). SEG was strongly negatively correlated with LYMPH (r = -0.947, p < 0.001), while MON demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with TLC (r = 0.435, p < 0.001).

Table 4

All established correlations

		Correlations											
		SEAG	TG	pH	PSG	GLU	TP	LDH	CHOL	TLC	SEG	MON	LYMPH
TLC	Correlation Coefficient	-.080	.195	.145	-.107	-.196	.357	.352	.287	1.000	.435	.308	-.488
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.326	.016	.076	.190	.016	<.001	<.001	<.001	.	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151
SEG	Correlation Coefficient	-.035	.161	.157	.010	-.228	.207	.409	.210	.435	1.000	.367	-.947
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.666	.048	.055	.906	.005	.011	<.001	.010	<.001	.	<.001	<.001
	N	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151
MON	Correlation Coefficient	-.049	.132	.027	.163	-.035	.104	.168	.101	.308	.367	1.000	-.561
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.547	.106	.738	.045	.668	.204	.039	.216	<.001	<.001	.	<.001
	N	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151
LYMPH	Correlation Coefficient	.072	-.191	-.141	-.058	.216	-.253	-.426	-.248	-.488	-.947	-.561	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.379	.019	.084	.482	.008	.002	<.001	.002	<.001	<.001	<.001	.
	N	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151

Discussion

The leukocyte subpopulation in malignant pleural effusions largely reflects the overall systemic response to the existing neoplasia. It represents tumor proliferation and increased vascular permeability, allowing white blood cells to enter the pleural space.

Focusing on patients with malignant pleural effusions, Tom Pettersson [10] conducted a study involving 140 patients who underwent diagnostic thoracentesis. On the same day, a pleural puncture sample and a blood sample were obtained from each patient. Seven of the 140 patients had pleural empyema, four had reactive pneumothorax as a result of treatment for pulmonary

tuberculosis, and one had pleural effusion following a pneumonectomy. These patients were excluded from the observation.

Of the remaining 128 patients, 86 had verified etiologies. Twenty-three had tuberculous pleural effusion, 24 had malignant pleural effusion, and five had malignant mesothelioma. Nineteen patients had secondary pleural involvement, most commonly from pulmonary adenocarcinoma. Seven patients had rheumatoid arthritis, four had systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), and two had sarcoidosis. One patient had chylothorax as a result of lymphoma. Total and differential leukocyte counts were performed on pleural fluid samples from all patients.

The conclusions indicated that transudative effusions contained fewer leukocytes compared to exudative ones. Different etiologies for transudative effusions did not show varying results. The most significant differences were observed in the lymphocyte population. Lymphocyte percentages were highest in tuberculous pleural effusions, exceeding 80%, and were also predominant in malignant effusions.

According to other sources, eosinophilia in pleural fluid is associated with chest trauma, pneumothorax, pulmonary infarction, and parasitic or fungal infections [11][12][13][14][15]. It is considered a good prognostic indicator for parapneumonic pleural effusions, as eosinophilic pleural effusions rarely progress to purulence. Neutrophilia with granulocyte predominance occurs in long-standing pleural effusions, while lymphocytes, aside from tuberculous and malignant pleural effusions, are also found in parapneumonic effusions [16].

From our analyses and the data obtained using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, total leukocyte count, segmented neutrophil count, monocyte count, and lymphocyte count showed non-normal parameter distribution. According to the results of the Independent Samples t-test, each parameter showed similar data variation in the equality of variances test. For the equality of means test, monocytes alone showed borderline values ($p=0.079$). When the Mann-Whitney U test was applied, total leukocyte count showed statistically significant differences between the two groups ($p=0.048$), monocyte count yielded the best results ($p=0.017$), and lymphocyte percentage showed a borderline value ($p=0.075$).

Therefore, in examining the differential distribution of white blood cell populations, we recommend investigating total leukocyte count, monocytes, and lymphocytes.

Conclusion

The study underscores the critical role of pleural fluid analysis in diagnosing and managing malignant pleural effusions. Leukocyte subpopulation profiling, particularly total leukocyte and monocyte counts, emerges as a robust diagnostic approach. Our findings advocate for integrating cytological and biochemical evaluations into routine clinical practice to enhance diagnostic precision and optimize therapeutic strategies. Further research is warranted to explore the prognostic implications of these parameters and refine their clinical utility in diverse patient populations.

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